

CYBERBULLYING: ITS SOCIAL AND ACADEMIC EFFECTS TO UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN THE PROVINCE OF CAPIZ

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Cyberbullying: Its Social and Academic Effects to Undergraduate Students in the Province of Capiz

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Abstract

This study investigated the extent of social and academic effects of cyberbullying victimization of undergraduate students in the province of Capiz. The mixed-method of research was utilized. The data needed for the study was gathered using the demographic profile for the profiling of the respondents, Cyberbullying Victimization Scale, Student Adjustment to College Questionnaire and the researcher-made focus group discussion guide. The Major findings of the study were (a) the extent of the entire cyberbullying victimizations was moderate, (b) the extent of the entire social effects of cyberbullying victimization was moderate, (d) the extent of the entire academic effects of cyberbullying victimization was high, (f) there are significant differences in the social, and academic effects among the extents of cyberbullying victimization.

Keywords: *cyberbullying, cyberbullying victimization, social, and academic*

Introduction

Online victimization and cyberbullying have gotten to be an unintended result of expanded understudy cooperation within the computerized world. The exponential development of the Web and its related computerized innovations over the final decade have without a doubt revolutionized the way understudies, companies and organizations communicate, trade thoughts, and remain associated around the world (Chisholm, 2014).

On the other hand, Malik & Obhi (2019), found out that social isolation, the experience of a person who has been ostracized from a social group, is a common effect of cybervictimization, as exclusion is a main tactic used in web-based cyberbullying. When a person is ostracized, it is common for them to lose a sense of agency because of removal from the group that facilitated their social mobility. Social agency is the feeling of control over one's actions and the effects of those actions.

Moreover, agreeing to Patchin et al. (2020), of those victimized by cyberbullying, numerous adolescents report genuine to serious wellbeing issues such as strong feelings of powerlessness, pity, uneasiness, fear and a failure to concentrate inside the school learning environment. Victims of cyberbullying are more likely to attain lower grades and report other scholastic issues as a result of the encounter.

Furthermore, failure to concentrate due to acts of cyberbullying can also be connected to poor academic performance and specifically associated to insufficiencies in student socialization levels (Peled, 2019). Other serious complications of cyberbullying include social confinement, depression, self-harm, suicidal ideation, and expanded use of illegal substances (Bauman et al., 2013). Reports also suggest that students who are cyberbullied are more inclined to then take an interest in cyberbullying, cyber stalking, and other forms of cyber hostility behavior, in this way perpetuating the online issue (Kowalski et al., 2014)

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the extent of social and academic effects of cyberbullying victimization of undergraduate students in the province of Capiz for the Academic Year 2022-2023. Specifically, the research investigation sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the entire and the top 5 cyberbullying victimizations of students?
2. What is the extent of the entire and the top 5 social effects of cyberbullying victimization of students?
3. What is the extent of the entire and the top 5 academic effects of cyberbullying victimization of undergraduate students?
4. Is there a significant difference in the social and academic effects among the extents of cyberbullying victimization of students?

Literature Review

Social and Academic Effects of Cyberbullying

Being bullied has a significantly negative effect on present and future students' performance in school. They show that bullying victims are powerless, shy, and anxious. They included that the victims' performance is poor in school, and they tend to avoid going to school classes for the reason of avoiding victimization. Victimization encountering can lead to poor academic performance and driving to absenteeism (Al-Raqad et al., 2017). Wong et al. (2014) that students who had a low sense of belonging at school were more involved in cyberbullying behaviors than were other students. Peled (2019) where Malaysian university found out that the majority of the participants (85%) interviewed shown that cyberbullying influenced their scholastic performance, particularly their grades.

Moreover, Kowalski and Limber (2013) stated that there is evidence that bullying may influence the scholastic work of bullied children. Children who are bullied are more likely than nonbullied peers to show that they want to avoid going to school, have higher absenteeism

rates, dislike school, and say that they receive poorer grades and lower standardized test scores. A meta-analysis of 33 studies found a significant negative association between peer victimization and scholastic accomplishment, as measured by grades, student achievement scores, or teacher ratings of academic achievement.

Likewise, Mehta et al. (2013) who found that when students feel that cyberbullying could be a phenomenon in their school, they feel that they are unsafe which reflected on less engaged in school community. Hence, they have less motivation to do well at school and they do not take an interest in school activities. Al-Raqqad et al. (2017) that cyberbullying has an effect on the student's performance either in a short or long term. She found that there are differences in relationship between cyberbullying level and scholastic performance depending on the student's scholarly achievement. He stated that 62% of learners who were victims of bullying did not pay attention to schoolwork and 5% said they were always considering of the bullies and of Hong et al. (2014) which confirmed that cyberbullied students commonly get lower grades and are at risk of poor scholastic performance.

On the other hand, Espelage et al. (2013) stated that mean or pitiless attacks on others can be made especially effortlessly within the computerized world since of a kind of "online disinhibition effect" or "anonymity". Kowalski and Limber (2013) when they inquired participants about the perceived effect of traditional bullying and cyberbullying, by inquiring whether participants thought cyberbullying had a greater or lesser effect than traditional bullying. Students in their study believed that bullying through use of a picture/video clip or in a chatroom would have a more noteworthy impact than traditional bullying.

Moreover, Wright et al. (2021) who examined the relationship between parental intervention, family support, and adolescents' use of problem-focused coping techniques toward cyberhate. They found that instructive intervention increases defensive adapting strategies such as distal advice, support from companions, assertiveness and specialized activities such as blocking the individual. In any case, it is worth noting that being cyber victimized is additionally associated with internalizing issues and avoidance behaviors, meaning victimized youth might not reach out for peer or familial support.

Furthermore, Xia and Li (2018) that the involvement of social confinement is related to a decrease in life fulfillment. It has appeared that feelings of social connection are related to general life fulfillment. These discoveries demonstrate that perceived social confinement can be a noteworthy mediator in life fulfillment and well-being. Delgado et al. (2020) that depressed students, having a high level or uneasiness or stress, may ended up victims of intimidation given their improper social behavior, lack of self-esteem or failure to defend themselves due to the depression, anxiety or stress that they are encountering. Additionally, a discouraged student with high levels of uneasiness or stress may have a low level of peer acknowledgment.

Results and Discussion

The Extent of the Entire and the Top 5 Cyberbullying Victimization of Students

The extent of the entire and the top 5 cyberbullying victimizations of students are shown in Table 1. Generally, the extent of the entire cyberbullying victimization of the students is moderate ($M = 2.79$, $SD = 0.92$).

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation of the Entire and Top 5 Cyberbullying Victimization

Variable	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Cyberbullying Victimization	2.79	Moderate	0.92
1. Being ignored and did not answer messages or things shared in groups or social networks.	3.35	Moderate	1.12
2. Being insulted or ridiculed in social networks or groups.	3.30	Moderate	1.01
3. Pretending or doing bad things on the internet.	3.02	Moderate	1.15
4. Being bothered and annoyed by taunting messages received.	2.98	Moderate	1.11
5. To make fun, photos or videos have been manipulated and uploaded or distributed on social networks.	2.97	Moderate	1.25

Legend: 4.21-5.00, Very High; 3.41-4.20, High; 2.61-3.40, Moderate; 1.81-2.60, Low; 1.00-1.80, Very Low

The results imply that cyberbullying among the undergraduate students in the province of Capiz is somehow manageable. Students can cope with the effects of cyberbullying even though they were affected temporarily. This does not give them a long-lasting effect because they do not internalize the effects of cyberbullying. The existence of cyberbullying might be due to the irresponsible, insensitive, and higher-level use of technologies and the increased availability of gadgets like smartphones. It is perhaps brought about by the social media influence and the negative climate in the college students' environment. Because of these, the online presence of the students increased significantly thus, they are prone to cyberbullying victimization.

The result is supported by the discussants in the focus group discussion. It showed the various ways in which cyberbullying affects individuals' personal identity, self-esteem, and emotional well-being. The discussants' experiences highlight the negative consequences of cyberbullying, including the distortion of one's online persona, feelings of isolation and shame, damage to self-esteem, and emotional distress. These cyberbullying actions lead to impersonation, verbal abuse and threats, public humiliation and mockery, discrimination and body shaming, betrayal and invasion of privacy, and psychological manipulation and extortion. It emphasizes the need for interventions and support systems to address and prevent cyberbullying, safeguarding individuals' mental health and personal identities in online spaces. This can explain that cyberbullying exists in the different forms as experienced by the students in some cases and these are:

Ignoring. It is the highest form of cyberbullying experience of the students. It is a subtle form of cyberbullying but it creates harm to some students when their messages, comments, or posts are not being given attention and worst disregarded as if they are not existing. In short, they are not valued and recognized in the social media. Even if they do post, comment, or message something positive, it is something as if nothing good happened.

Insulting or ridiculing. It is often experienced by the victims of cyberbullying. This behavior is inflated by the egos of those who cyberbully, motivated by their anger, and surrounded by insecurities. If the victim is shamed then the insulter(cyberbully) felt happy by their own doing. They felt superior and feel good if they insulted or ridiculed others in social networks or groups.

As shared by discussant 2, flaming is prevalent:

Discussant 2. *I experienced being bullied on social media by an unknown person. I shared something on Facebook about basketball and my caption would be like "pakialamera ang pang apat" and a lot of millennials were doing it also because it is a trend and its only for fun for us...*

(I experienced being bullied on social media by an unknown person. I shared something on Facebook about basketball and my caption was like "the fourth person doesn't mind his/her own business" and a lot of millennials were doing it also because it is a trend and its only for fun for us...)

The result confirms the study of Martínez-Monteaquedo et al. (2020) that cyberbullies, who are highly skilled in these new digital scenarios, rely on these technologies to carry out aggressive behavior toward their peers (threats, harassment, bribes, insults, humiliation, publication of confidential information identity theft, manipulation of photographs, recording, and dissemination of physical aggressions, etc.).

Impersonation. This is when the cyberbully impersonates the victim online, creating a false profile or pretending to be the victim saying embarrassing or mean messages in order to create a bad reputation against the victim online. The reason for this is that the perpetrator knows that by using his real identity to attack someone else he could create trouble to himself. Instead, by using the identity of others, it could shift the attention to the name of the account that he/she is using.

As shared by discussant 1, fake accounts are prevalent:

Discussant 1. *"Someone I don't know created a fake account of me and started posting explicit graphics and even videos and also spreading falsified information about other people..."*

As shared also by discussant 8, impersonation is prevalent:

Discussant 8. *The first time that I was experienced cyberbullying is when I was at grade 8 level it is very look like scandal because one of our classmates edit a photo with a picture that don't have clothes like nothing "talaga" ...*

(The first time that I experienced cyberbullying is when I was at grade 8 level, it looks like a scandal because one of our classmates edited a photo with a picture that don't have clothes like really nothing...)

Moreover, as expressed by discussants 9 and 10, impersonation is prevalent:

Discussant 9. *Cyberbullying is one of the major aspects of why I am an introverted person. I experienced cyberbullying when I was in Senior High school when one of my teachers put my name on the list to join in one of the big events in school..*

Discussant 10. *This happened only a month ago and there was also a few years ago where someone was making accounts using my pictures and information and last month, he was constantly commenting bad words on my photos on Facebook, making group chats and calling on my cellphone my number to talk bad and threaten me that if I didn't pay my cousin's debt, they would post my picture on the internet...*

The result affirms the study of Kowalski and Limber (2013) when they inquired participants about the perceived effect of traditional bullying and cyberbullying, by inquiring whether participants thought cyberbullying had a greater or lesser effect than traditional bullying. Students in their study believed that bullying through use of a picture/video clip or in a chatroom would have a more noteworthy impact than traditional bullying.

Mean or Hurtful Messages. Cyberbullies use the social media to destroy the character and reputation of the students. They send a false report to damage another's reputation. They are the cyberbullies who are bored in life and have nothing to do except destroy the character and image of others.

As expressed by the following discussants, harassment is prevalent:

Discussant 3. *"As a cyberbullying victims experienced what they call doxing or revealing my sensitive or personal information just to embarrass and humiliates me by spreading my personal photos in public..."*

Discussant 4. *"I was the victim of this cyberbullying case last March 2023, and that day I started to receive mean and threatening text*

messages from someone I didn't know...”.

Discussant 5. *I had many experiences of cyberbullying but the one who really gave an impact to me was the recently valentines day, Feb 14 2023 when someone I know and someone I trust had posted my epic photo to social media for FUN but that because of that photo people freely mocked me, criticize my appearance and even my attitude towards the photo...*

Discussant 6. “Someone posted in my profile pic and they criticize and throw offensive words about my physical appearance just because I have way darker skin before, and I felt very discriminated in a way, because they commented it in facebook...”.

The result concurs with the findings of Espelage et al. (2013) that mean or pitiless attacks on others can be made especially effortlessly within the computerized world since of a kind of “online disinhibition effect” or “anonymity”.

The Extent of the Entire and the Top 5 Social Effects of Cyberbullying Victimization

The extent of the entire and the top 5 social effects of cyberbullying victimizations of students is shown in Table 2. Generally, the extent of the entire social effects of cyberbullying victimization of students is moderate ($M = 3.30$, $SD = 0.66$).

Table 2. *Mean and Standard Deviation of the Extent of the Entire and the Top 5 Social Effects of Cyberbullying Victimization*

Variable	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Social Effects	3.30	Moderate	0.66
1. Having some good friends or acquaintances at college.	3.71	High	1.02
2. Getting along very well with roommates at college.	3.67	High	0.88
3. Quite satisfied with social life at college	3.52	High	0.92
4. Meeting as many people, and making as many friends at college.	3.46	High	0.99
5. Having close social ties at college.	3.41	High	0.78

Legend: 4.21-5.00, Very High; 3.41-4.20, High; 2.61-3.40, Moderate; 1.81-2.60, Low; 1.00-1.80, Very Low

The result implies that the undergraduate students in the province of Capiz have maintained their interpersonal relationships and social communication skills with their classmates, peers, teachers, and their parents despite being cyberbullied. They have the support networks with whom they feel safe, can trust, and share their experiences with cyberbullying. Students isolate themselves temporarily because they feel not mentally stable and not ready to face the society. This isolation does not last longer because they have the support group like their friends, family members, or teachers wherein they could share about how they feel. This shows that students have balanced interpersonal relationship as their social communication with each other, and with other members of society, and their participation with others in social events are not really affected. They remain to be opened to them. These findings indicate the existence of a distinct state of social communication among community members in the environment in which the study tool was applied.

The result of the finding is congruent to the views of the discussants in the focus group discussion which delved into the profound effects of cyberbullying on individuals' social lives and overall well-being. Through a series of personal accounts and experiences shared by the participants, it showed the various ways in which cyberbullying has shaped their interactions, emotions, and choices within their social spheres. The focus group shed light on the consequences such as withdrawal, selective event participation, decreased self-esteem, anxiety, trust issues, isolation, and the reshaping of social circles. By delving into these experiences, we seek to raise awareness about the detrimental effects of cyberbullying and foster a better understanding of its psychological and social impact.

Opening-up. Opening up means being honest and vulnerable and letting others know how you are truly feeling. Sometimes this can also mean learning to be honest with yourself. Opening up to people can help victims gain perspective and find solutions that they may not have been able to reach on their own. Sharing their experiences can also help them feel less alone.

However, most of the students find it difficult to open-up their problems with anyone since they lost their trust. They felt depressed. They feel like they want to be alone.

As confirmed by discussants 2, 4, and 9, decreased self-esteem is prevalent among cyberbullied students.

Discussant 2. *“So, the effect of cyberbullying in my social life made me feel drowned even though that time I know that I am the victim but because I cannot predict the minds of other people...”.*

Discussant 4. *The effect of cyberbullying in my social life was significant. It became rejoined and isolated. I'm avoiding social events and choosing to spend more time alone. I felt like I couldn't trust anyone not even my boyfriend and closest friends...*

Discussant 9. *For me Sir in my social life, I don't want to go home in our Barangay. I think it's last month that I saw one of my trusted friends mocking me with one of our friends also. I saw my Name in the comment. And I accidentally know that they always talk about something bad about me. So I am wondering why those people whom I trust did something terrible to me. And drives me to lose everything I built for how many years.*

The result affirms the findings of Wright et al. (2021) who examined the relationship between parental intervention, family support,

and adolescents' use of problem-focused coping techniques toward cyberhate. They found that instructive intervention increases defensive adapting strategies such as distal advice, support from companions, assertiveness and specialized activities such as blocking the individual. In any case, it is worth noting that being cyber victimized is additionally associated with internalizing issues and avoidance behaviors, meaning victimized youth might not reach out for peer or familial support.

Adaptability. Being adaptable means being able to adjust from different kinds of negative situations, environment, and events (crisis) that victims experienced or circumstances that made them part of the group. Students can be resilient when faced by the difficult challenges. They can bounce back from the effects of cyberbullying since they have self-confidence and determination to face this problem.

However, there are those student victims who have a hard time facing the challenges brought by the cyberbullying. As a result, they would lack self-confidence and become disappointed with their selves.

Discussants 5, 7, and 8 have expressed that lack of confidence is prevalent among the victims of cyberbullying.

Discussant 5. *So, the effect of cyberbullying to my social life of course I have the same effect together with participant number 3. I always feel that when I walk to school I always think people will talk about me. Thinking that they are talking about me even though maybe that I am not...*

Discussant 7. *Sir, I lost my interest in making friends in my social life then I also deactivated my social media accounts. And not being active, because I am afraid to go with my friends and interact with them because I felt like being judged every time...*

Discussant 8. *For me, I feel like I don't want to go to school any more because every time I entered our classroom they always said that maybe it is true about the picture I have spreading on social media. And I am also scared to socialize with other people especially to the people I know and already know about the picture...*

This study confirms the findings of Al-Raqad et al. (2017) who stated that being bullied has a significantly negative effect on present and future students' performance in school. They show that bullying victims are powerless, shy, and anxious. They included that the victims' performance is poor in school, and they tend to avoid going to school classes for the reason of avoiding victimization. Victimization encountering can lead to poor academic performance and driving to absenteeism.

Contentment. Being contented with your life means that you are satisfied with what you have and that includes your social spheres. Your contentment relies on your specific needs, interests, values, and goals. And you don't need to prove your contentment to anyone else. When you are contented, you have greater self-awareness and better understanding how to communicate your emotions and thoughts.

However, most of the students feel that there is something lacking in their lives as a result of cyberbullying.

As expressed by discussant 6, being doubtful is prevalent among the cyberbullied students.

Discussant 6. *"I've been a cold person. I never trust anyone, and I felt like anyone who can get too close to me will just discriminate me and not accept me for who I am."*

The result affirms the study of Xia and Li (2018) that the involvement of social confinement is related to a decrease in life fulfillment. It has appeared that feelings of social connection are related to general life fulfillment. These discoveries demonstrate that perceived social confinement can be a noteworthy mediator in life fulfillment and well-being.

Sociability. A sociable person is someone who is friendly, welcoming, and ready for activities with others. A sociable person has the ability to establish contact and conduct a conversation with people of different ages and backgrounds. A sociable person is also curious and open-minded, taking interest in what others think and feel.

However, cyberbullying makes it difficult for victims to meet new people and make new friends because they are anxious with their environment. This could lead to losing their trust with others because they felt depressed, embarrassed, and humiliated.

Discussants 1 and 3 affirmed that social withdrawal is prevalent among the victims of cyberbullying.

Discussant 1. *"So the effect Sir of cyberbullying in my social life that my social battery and social energy really deteriorated and I don't have the energy to socialize with other people any time of the day..."*

Discussant 3. *"So the effects of cyberbullying in my social life is I lost my self-esteem that time because it happened when I was in Senior High School. I lost interest in interacting with other people and social media..."*

Moreover, discussant 10 reiterated that shamefulness is prevalent among the cyberbullies:

Discussant 10. *First, I'm ashamed that some people will think that I'm as stupid as the people who told me on Facebook but in the end, I just let it go and I blocked their accounts and numbers and deleted their comments on my Facebook post.*

The result affirms the findings of Delgado et al. (2020) that depressed students, having a high level of uneasiness or stress, may ended

up victims of intimidation given their improper social behavior, lack of self-esteem or failure to defend themselves due to the depression, anxiety or stress that they are encountering. Additionally, a discouraged student with high levels of uneasiness or stress may have a low level of peer acknowledgment.

The Extent of the Entire and the Top 5 Academic Effects of Cyberbullying Victimization

The extent of the entire and the top 3 academic effects of cyberbullying victimizations of students is shown in Table 3. Generally, the extent of the entire academic effects of cyberbullying victimization of students is high ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.53$).

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation of the Extent of the Entire and the Top 5 Academic Effects of Cyberbullying Victimization.

Variable	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Academic Effects	3.42	High	0.53
1. Attending classes regularly.	4.00	High	1.04
2. Keeping up to date with the academic work.	3.58	High	0.89
3. Quite satisfied with academic situation at college	3.56	High	0.90
4. Enjoying academic work at college.	3.53	High	0.86
5. Not really smart enough for academic work expected to be doing now.	3.46	High	0.82

Legend: 4.21-5.00, Very High; 3.41-4.20, High; 2.61-3.40, Moderate; 1.81-2.60, Low; 1.00-1.80, Very Low

The result implies that cyberbullying is seen by the students to be positive towards their academic performance. They take cyberbullying as a challenge and not as a hindrance to go on with their studies. Generally, they made their experiences with cyberbullying as a motivation to learn, taking actions to meet with academic demands, a clear sense of purpose and general satisfaction with their academic environment.

However, cyberbullying can affect the victims' ability to concentrate, study effectively, and maintain motivation. More specifically, if the perpetrator was known to be one of their classmates, school mates, or even teachers, the cyberbully victims would avoid going to school. And even the perpetrator was not known, the students would be anxious with their surroundings, suspecting everyone who might do it.

That is why they lose interest in their concentration and motivations in their study, would always be absent and not going to school anymore that could result in a decline to their academic performance and loss of interest in school-related activities.

The result is supported by the discussants in the focus group discussion. Some of them expressed that their academic performance or achievement is hampered, and they need to strive harder or struggle in order to cope up with their academic behavior and performance in school. However, some participants demonstrate resilience and adopt strategies to overcome these challenges, emphasizing the importance of perseverance and a positive mindset in the face of cyberbullying.

Self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is the belief of students in their ability to complete a task or achieve a goal. It encompasses their confidence to control their behavior, exert an influence over their environment, and stay motivated in the pursuit of their goal. Students can have self-efficacy in different situations and domains, such as school, relationships, and other important areas.

However, when faced by the cyberbullying situation, students feel being unmotivated and loss their interest to accomplish their goal, and they also feel like giving up. They doubt their own abilities to rise up and overcome the difficulties that life throws their way. They do not like to keep going in the face of obstacles.

According to discussants 1, 3, and 8 loss of interest is commonly experienced by them as victims of cyberbullying.

Discussant 1. *"As for my studies, cyberbullying also really took a great toll because my academic life has been greatly affected. So, not to brag but, when I was in High School, I was an academic achiever..."*

Discussant 3. *"So, I can describe the effect of cyberbully in my studies, "sadto nga times, may mga times nga nadula akon interest sakon pageskwela tungod gani sakon mga ginapinanundom"..."*

(*"So, I can describe the effect of cyberbullying in my studies as very negative because I lost interest in studying just because of overthinking what had happened to me..."*.)

Discussant 8. *"The effect of cyberbullying on my academic is that I feel loss interest in going to school and laziness in doing the activities..."*

On the contrary discussant 9 reiterated that he/she felt motivated in spite of being cyberbullied.

Discussant 9. *"For me, I think cyberbullying didn't affect my studies sir, "kay wala man ko may nakita nga hindrance everytime nga may ano ko may ara o may napanundom sina" ..."*

(*"For me, I think cyberbullying didn't affect my studies sir, because I didn't really experience having any difficulties personally in that*

area...”.)

The result concurs with the discoveries of Kowalski and Limber (2013) that there is evidence that bullying may influence the scholastic work of bullied children. Children who are bullied are more likely than nonbullied peers to show that they want to avoid going to school, have higher absenteeism rates, dislike school, and say that they receive poorer grades and lower standardized test scores.

A meta-analysis of 33 studies found a significant negative association between peer victimization and scholastic accomplishment, as measured by grades, student achievement scores, or teacher ratings of academic achievement.

Determination. Determination refers to a student's ability to make choices and manage their own life. Being determined means that students feel in greater control of their lives. Students' determination impacts their academic motivation. Students are more likely to feel motivated to achieve and also to feel greater levels of competence and satisfaction.

However, most students are distracted by the mental stress brought by the cyberbullying. Thus, it makes them feel unmotivated with their studies.

Discussants 2, 5, 6, and 7 reiterated that they all experienced loss of motivation as victims of cyberbullying.

Discussant 2. *I can describe the effect of cyberbullying in my studies in a way that I lost concentration in doing all of my homework and school activities at home. But in the grace of Lord, actually, I am not really affected by the cyberbullying that happened to me because I really value my education above all...*

Discussant 5. *The effect of cyberbullying in my academic life is that I lost interest on my studies. “Just like man bala sir nga nagaprocrastinate na ko sakon nga mga modules. Sang una kung may mag send insigida ga answer ko. Yanda natamanan na ko kay I feel nga nakaffect man gyapon atong pagpost sang picture” ...*

(The effect of cyberbullying in my academic life is that I lost interest on my studies. I really procrastinated a lot, ‘before the moment the modules are uploaded, I instantly answer it, but after what had happened it seems like I lost the interest in opening those tasks solely because I can still remember that picture posted...)

Discussant 6. *“In my studies, I can say that I put it behind that much because it became as one of my coping mechanisms to distract me from problems on social media...”*

Discussant 7. *“I also lost interest in school, doing homework and activities. Also, I don't participate in any school curricular activities and some events...”*

This result affirms the study of Peled (2019) where Malaysian university found out that the majority of the participants (85%) interviewed shown that cyberbullying influenced their scholastic performance, particularly their grades.

Satisfaction. Student satisfaction is defined as the perception of contentment with university experiences, and the extent to which students feel their expectations for their learning are met while at an academic institution. Student satisfaction is being shaped continually by repeated experiences in campus life.

Productive. Productivity means to be efficient. It means that students produce a desired result for a given output. What makes the students to be productive is their desire to finish their studies. Therefore, they would do everything like keeping their academic performance balanced.

One of the reasons students lack productivity is the lack of concentration. Students cannot concentrate in their studies because of the emotional turmoil brought by cyberbullying. They can be easily distracted resulting to their unproductive. Their goals and motivation in their studies are affected which they lost interest academically.

As shared by discussant 4, he lost concentration as a victim of cyberbullying.

Discussant 4. *So, cyberbullying had a significant effect on my concentration skills. I find it hard to really gain information and I struggled to remember what I had learned, and I was constantly checking on my phone kung may message. My mind was consumed with worry and fear...*

The result affirms the study of Al-Raqqad et al. (2017) which stated that 62% of learners who were victims of bullying did not pay attention to schoolwork and 5% said they were always considering of the bullies and of Hong et al. (2014) which confirmed that cyberbullied students commonly get lower grades and are at risk of poor scholastic performance.

Doubting. Low self-esteem or lack of confidence leaves students doubting their ability to succeed, making them hesitant to engage in learning or take appropriate academic growth risks. Students are reluctant to try new things or be unable to tolerate typical levels of frustration. They also may pretend they don't care, or may be aggressive to cover up their lack of confidence.

The result affirms the findings of Wong et al. (2014) that students who had a low sense of belonging at school were more involved in cyberbullying behaviors than were other students.

Difference in the Social Effects among the Extents of Cyberbullying Victimization of Students

Table 4 presents the difference in social effects among the extents of cyberbullying victimization of students. The result showed that there is a significant difference in social effects among the extents of cyberbullying victimization of students ($F = 6.55$, $Sig = 0.00$).

Table 4. *Difference of the Social Effects among the Levels of Cyberbullying Victimization*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Between Groups	9.55	4	2.4	6.554*	0.000
Within Groups	36.8	101	0.4		
Total	46.3	105			

* $p < 0.05$ significant @ 5% alpha level

The result implies that the higher the level of cyberbullying victimization, the higher are the social effects. This might be based on the persistence of the attacks of cyberbully to the victims. That is the reason why students would isolate themselves, having trust issues that would make them find new friends and makes them hard to communicate, afraid of their surroundings because anyone could be a suspect, and they felt drowned and having no energy to face the society. The marks of the negative experiences of the victims remain for a certain period of time until time heals and vanishes this bitter experience.

Results of the study are congruent to the testimonies of the discussants in the focus group discussion as they claimed that cyberbullying had a negative impact in their social life. For instance, trust issues and the decision to isolate themselves from others in social settings were also mentioned, reflecting the impact on the participants' social lives.

As emphasized by discussants 1, 3, and 9, anxiousness is felt by them as victims of cyberbullying.

Discussant 1: *"While in my social life I became adamant. I was lonely alone and very anxious around people especially in big crowds"*.

Discussant 3: *In terms of my social life, I became aware of who I will trust and until now it's always in my mind that I don't need many friends I will be contented of being alone sometime that to go with others, because now I believe that more friends more judgement you will have if you fail.*

Discussant 9: *"I distant myself to other people and I lost trust to them and when it comes to social life"*.

Moreover, discussants 2, 4, 5, and 7 experienced isolation as a result of being cyberbullied.

Discussant 2: *"In my social life, cyberbullying can also have negative impact on me because in my social life, I'll be isolating them from peers like "kagina nga gin hambal ko" it causes me to withdraw from social activities"*.

(*"In my social life, cyberbullying also had negative impacts on me because in my social life, I'll be isolating myself from peers like what I said earlier it causes me to withdraw from social activities"*.)

Discussant 4: *"On my social life, there is something like social isolation, explosion and lack of trust and others"*.

Discussant 5: *"In the social life, my circle of friends became smaller, and I lost my interest to socialization"*.

Discussant 7: *"Lacking in socialization and making some friends every time we're going outside or in a crowded place"*.

For discussant 6 and 10, loss of confidence is prevalent:

Discussant 6: *"In my social life, I had no confidence to interact with people"*.

Discussant 10: *"I don't have that kind of energy to face the people around me"*.

On the other hand, discussant suffered from both loneliness and isolation.

Discussant 8: *"Yes, the connections of this to cyberbullying, is that victims typically display loneliness and social exclusion"*.

Results of the study support the findings of Mehta et al. (2013) who found that when students feel that cyberbullying could be a phenomenon in their school, they feel that they are unsafe which reflected on less engaged in school community. Hence, they have less motivation to do well at school and they do not take an interest in school activities.

Difference in the Academic Effects among the Extents of Cyberbullying Victimization of Students

Table 5 presents the difference in academic effects among the extents of cyberbullying victimization of students. The result showed that there is a significant difference in academic effects or behavior among the college students when classified according to their levels of cyberbullying victimization ($F = 10.101$, $Sig = 0.00$).

The result implies that the more the students experienced cyberbullying, the more it has an intense effect towards their academic performance. They would be bothered too much which makes them lost their focus and concentration in class resulting to a decline in their grades. They would also feel depressed resulting in isolation and not going to school anymore. This shows the intense effect of cyberbullying that impacts negatively their studies as they are not emotionally and mentally stable.

Table 5. *Difference of the Academic Effects Among the Levels of Cyberbullying Victimization*

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	Sig.
Between Groups	8.45	4	2.1	10.101*	0.000
Within Groups	21.1	101	0.2		
Total	29.6	105			

* $p < 0.05$ significant @ 5% alpha level

Results of this study are congruent to the testimonies of the discussants in the focus group discussion as they claimed that cyberbullying had a negative impact in their emotional state. Participants mention a decline in their academic performance, loss of interest in studying, procrastination, and difficulty concentrating. Motivation to participate in school activities is diminished, and some participants contemplate giving up on their studies altogether. Cyberbullying becomes a significant distraction, leading to a lack of focus and a struggle to retain information.

In addition, the findings of the study confirm with the stories of the discussants as they claimed that cyberbullying had a negative impact in their emotional state. Participants mentioned a decline in their academic performance, loss of interest in studying, procrastination, and difficulty concentrating. Motivation to participate in school activities was diminished, and some participants contemplated giving up on their studies altogether. Cyberbullying became a significant distraction, leading to a lack of focus and a struggle to retain information.

As expressed by discussants 1 and 5, they lost their interest in their studies.

Discussant 1: *In my academic life, as what I have said before, before I was really patted, I was really driven of my studies but after what had happened, I handed off interest, and I procrastinated a lot, something that I wit upon so that, I can get back on them.*

Discussant 5: *"In my academic life, I lost interest in my study that leads to low grades and scores to my exams that's all".*

For discussants 2 and 9, they lost motivation for school activities.

Discussant 2: *"In my academic life, it really had a negative effects on me, to my academic performances because sometimes I loss motivations to participate in school activities so that's all".*

Discussant 9: *In academic life, "I don't think na may ara kay feeling ko indi man apektado akon studies sadto, kag daw indi ko man siya nakikita nga reason na para maapektuhan ang akon nga study especially nga ang rasyu nga ginahatag sakon sakon fam. Daw indi ko nagid siya masabay didto".*

(*"In academic life, I don't think that it has a significant effect, simply because that I don't see it as one, and as a matter of fact I considered the bullying as my motivation to study harder"*.)

On the part of discussants 3, 4, 6, and 10, they lost concentration in their studies.

Discussant 3: *I lost hope that causes to loss my concentration and interest to my study. Some of my subjects had been affected. And that time it comes to my mind just to stop my study because I feel that it was nonsense.*

Discussant 4: *"On my academic life, cyberbullying affect my performance loss of concentration and lack of motivation".*

Discussant 6: *"To my academic life, although I can say that it made me more intricated in my studies, I can't still control myself when I get distracted when I'm reading or studying just because I remembered what happened to me".*

Discussant 10: *"I felt depressed and cannot concentrate in class. As if that I don't feel like going to school anymore".*

Whereas, for discussants 7 and 8, academic struggle was their challenge.

Discussant 7: *"In academic life, we struggle to commit in school activities and doing our homework on time".*

Discussant 8: *"Yes, the connections of this to cyberbullying, is that victims typically display school phobias, and poor academic achievement".*

Findings of this study support the findings of Al-Raqqad et al. (2017) that cyberbullying has an effect on the student's performance either in a short or long term. She found that there are differences in relationship between cyberbullying level and scholastic performance depending on the student's scholarly achievement.

Conclusions

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